

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

OPTIMIZATION OF BIG DATA STREAM PROCESSING IN APPLIED IT SERVICES: EXPERIENCE IN DESIGNING PRODUCTION-GRADE SOLUTIONS

Bogutskii A.

Bachelor's Degree,

ITMO University,

St Petersburg, Russia,

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-3996-5269>

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Abstract

This article studies engineering and architectural approaches to building big data stream processing systems in applied IT services operating under conditions of high dynamics and variable load. The requirements for industrial streaming solutions are considered, including scalability, fault tolerance, state management, latency control, and ensuring data consistency in a distributed environment. Modern architectural models for organizing event processing, mechanisms for adapting to changing data streams, and methods for optimizing the performance of streaming pipelines are examined. Based on real-world cases from large technology companies, the impact of streaming architecture on reducing processing latency and improving infrastructure stability is demonstrated.

Keywords: *Stream Data Processing, Big Data, Distributed Computing, Information System Architecture, Apache Flink, Kafka Streams, Scalability, Fault Tolerance.*

1. Introduction

Digital transformation of applied IT services is accompanied by a steady growth in the volume and speed of data generation. E-commerce, financial platforms, telecommunication and Internet of Things (IoT) systems generate continuous streams of events that require processing not retrospectively, but directly at the moment they occur. Traditional batch analysis methods based on periodic aggregation and delayed computations prove to be insufficiently effective under conditions of high business process dynamics, where the value of information rapidly decreases over time. Under these conditions, stream processing technologies become particularly important, ensuring continuous extraction of knowledge from data and supporting decision-making in real time.

Along with the growing interest in stream computing, the requirements for processing infrastructure are also becoming more complex. Modern production IT services must support horizontal scalability, operate reliably under uneven and peak loads, guarantee data integrity, and provide predictable response latency. In practice, this leads to the need to design specialized architectures that combine distributed computing, state management, fault tolerance mechanisms, and flexible integration tools with applied systems. At the same time, it is insufficient to consider streaming technologies solely as software tools: the architectural level itself begins to play a key role, determining the efficiency of resource utilization and the operational characteristics of solutions.

Despite the active development of corresponding platforms and frameworks, a part of publications is either theoretical in nature or describes individual technical aspects without an analysis of their applicability in industrial environments. In engineering practice, a gap still remains between the capabilities of stream processing technologies and a systematic approach to their

implementation in real services. Generalization of accumulated experience in building production solutions, identification of stable architectural patterns, and evaluation of their impact on the performance indicators of applied IT applications are required. The goal of this research is to study and systematize architectural and engineering approaches to optimizing big data stream processing in applied IT services, as well as to analyze practical experience in implementing production solutions in terms of their scalability, reliability, and impact on business process efficiency.

2. Main part

2.1. Requirements for fault-tolerant data transmission channels in distributed systems

The continuous growth in the volume and speed of incoming data in modern information systems requires a transition from traditional batch processing models to continuous, stream-based computing. Stream data processing represents continuous analysis of incoming events with minimal latency, which makes it possible to make decisions and generate responses in real time. This approach is especially in demand in areas where reaction time to incoming data is a critical factor. These can be listed as fintech solutions (transaction analysis and fraud detection), digital e-commerce platforms (order processing and personalization), and IoT ecosystems (device monitoring and telemetry) [1].

The key engineering task in building stream systems is to ensure a balance between several interrelated system requirements: scalability, reliability, predictable response latency, efficient state management, and the ability to recover after failures. The workload in many industrial stream applications is highly variable and unpredictable: activity peaks may occur in waves, and the distribution of events is often uneven in time and space, which complicates the design of a stable architecture.

In addition, strict guarantees of result consistency are achieved in engineering stream processing systems despite the distributed nature of computations, heterogeneity of incoming streams, and the possibility of failures of individual components. Structurally, ensuring

fault tolerance of stream systems is associated both with the characteristics of state storage and with data processing parameters. The main components and metrics affecting the stability of a stream platform are presented in fig. 1.

Figure 1. Classification of fault tolerance methods in stream data processing systems [2]

In addition, another important engineering principle is the separation of responsibilities between system layers: from data sources and message brokers to the processing system and delivery of results to the user. Such a multilayer approach makes it possible to decompose the system into independent components, each of which is responsible for a narrow set of tasks: event collection and routing, buffering and queue control, computation and aggregation, storage, and delivery of results to consuming services.

The engineering formulation of the task of optimizing big data stream processing goes beyond the traditional design of distributed computing systems. It requires a comprehensive combination of state management methods, scaling mechanisms, fault tolerance provision, and active system telemetry management, which together form the basis for creating production IT solutions capable of effectively supporting the requirements of modern business.

2.2. Architectural approaches to optimizing big data stream processing

Modern stream data processing systems face enormous volumes and speeds of data, which is especially

noticeable in the era of big data and the IoT. In some scenarios, the data streams reach hundreds of millions of messages per second. Such loads are typical for e-commerce, financial technologies, and IoT, where performance requirements are particularly high. To support such scenarios, architectural solutions are required that ensure scalability, adaptability to load, and stability of stream data pipelines.

One of the basic principles of modern stream systems is **event-driven architecture**. In such systems, components react to incoming events asynchronously, which eliminates rigid synchronous coupling between modules and increases the overall responsiveness and scalability of the solution. Data processing is built around events: each event (message, log entry, signal from a sensor, etc.) immediately triggers the corresponding processing without waiting for batch collection of data. When comparing the two existing interaction models, the asynchronous model better corresponds to the requirements of big data stream processing (table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of event-driven architecture and synchronous request-response model [3]		
Aspect	Event-driven architecture	Synchronous request-response
Communication	Asynchronous, event-based.	Synchronous, blocking calls.
Scalability	Highly scalable, services operate independently.	Limited by request queue capacity.
Fault tolerance	High resilience, retries can be handled independently.	Failure in one service affects the entire request chain
Latency	Lower latency for large-scale workloads.	Higher latency due to request dependencies.
Best suited for	Real-time analytics, IoT, financial transactions, microservices.	Monolithic systems, synchronous Application Programming Interfaces.

The evolution of the event-driven approach led to the emergence of architectures initially designed with priority given to data streams (“stream-first”). In such **architectures, streaming data is treated as a first-class object**: even batch processing is considered a special case of stream processing – limited by size or time. An example is Apache Flink, which was originally created as a streaming engine, in which the sequential stream of events is considered the single “source of truth” for computations. As a result, stream-first systems (also known as Kappa-type architectures) simplify the data processing stack: they use one unified stream-

ing pipeline for both historical and new data, eliminating the need to maintain separate contours for batch and stream processing.

An alternative approach, which became widespread in the 2010s, is a **hybrid model** that combines separate pipelines for batch and stream processing. A classic example is the Lambda architecture. In the Lambda architecture, data passes through two pipelines in parallel: (1) the speed layer processes the stream of events in real time with minimal latency, producing operational but possibly approximate results; (2) the batch layer periodically reprocesses the accumulated complete dataset (data at rest) to compute accurate results, correcting possible errors of the speed layer (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Conceptual diagram of Lambda architecture [4]

Further, the results of both layers are combined at the serving layer to provide consistent responses to user requests. This approach ensures a balance between performance and accuracy: the fast streaming layer sacrifices part of the accuracy for the sake of minimal latency, while the batch layer guarantees “eventual consistency” by recomputing results with high precision from the complete dataset.

One of the key **problems** in large stream systems is **load variability**. The volume of incoming data and the rate of event arrival can change dramatically over time (spikes in user activity during a promotion in e-commerce or a sharp increase in IoT sensor traffic during certain events). The stream processing architecture must be able to adapt to such load changes while maintaining the required level of performance [5].

Horizontal scaling of the streaming pipeline is a necessary condition for processing fluctuating data volumes in real time. Unlike batch tasks, which are relatively short-lived, streaming applications operate continuously, therefore they must be able to dynamically change the amount of involved resources (the number of nodes, threads, executors) in order to adapt to the current data stream.

Even with a sufficient number of resources, **load imbalance may occur between parallel streaming tasks**. This is especially relevant for stateful operators that partition work by keys (for example, key-based aggregations or stream joins). If the key distribution is uneven (so-called skew), some operator instances receive a much larger data flow (“hot” keys) and become bottlenecks.

The simplest approach – static hash partitioning of keys across multiple nodes – does not solve the prob-

lem when the load pattern changes dynamically. Adaptive balancing strategies are required. One solution is on-the-fly regrouping of keys based on their current frequency. In one study, the Aj-Stream system was proposed for adaptive load balancing under skew in join operations. It applies prediction of key “hotness” using a neural network (a sequential GRU-based model) and pre-adjusts the key distribution scheme before a sharp change in event frequency occurs. Compared to traditional systems, adaptive balancing increased throughput by about 22% and reduced average latency almost by half under frequently fluctuating data streams [6].

Another mechanism for dealing with imbalance is automatic redistribution of “hot” keys across several nodes (i.e., partition splitting). For example, if a certain Kafka partition or a state partition is overloaded, the system may temporarily duplicate this partition to two nodes and route part of the keys to the second one. In general, stream balancing at the architectural level includes monitoring load metrics on each node (for example, CPU utilization, queue sizes, processing time per key) and making decisions about load relocation – whether reassignment of keys, adding operator replicas, or even load shedding in extreme cases.

State is a key element of streaming applications, allowing the accumulation of intermediate data and performing aggregation, session processing, and analytical computations in real time. As the load increases, the state volume may reach gigabytes and terabytes, which requires architectural mechanisms for fast access and reliable storage of data. Modern streaming platforms implement state management through periodic checkpoints and moving storage to durable distributed systems, which ensures recovery after failures and ex-

actly-once processing semantics. Decoupling computation and state storage, using external file systems, and asynchronous snapshots make it possible to reduce latency, simplify scaling, and shorten recovery time after failures.

The **stability of stream processing** is also determined by the system's ability to maintain acceptable latency under changing input intensity. For this purpose, mechanisms for controlling processing speed and regulating load are used, including adapting window sizes, limiting message queues, and backpressure – transmitting a slowdown signal from overloaded consumers to data sources.

Such methods prevent buffer overflow, reduce the risk of performance degradation, and ensure predictable system behavior even under peak loads. Together, state management, fault tolerance, and flow control form the basis of the architectural stability of modern big data stream processing platforms.

2.3. Practical experience in building and implementing production solutions in applied IT services

The accumulated industrial background of implementing streaming architectures in applied IT services

may indicate the high practical value of these approaches. The practice of operating such solutions demonstrates their ability to ensure scalability, resistance to load fluctuations, and economical use of resources, as well as to positively influence the efficiency of business processes by reducing processing latency and increasing service reliability.

The online review service **Yelp** modernized its data platform by moving from cumbersome batch processing to a hybrid streaming lakehouse architecture. The company implemented a streaming pipeline based on Apache Flink and a new storage system, Apache Paimon, with data stored in Amazon S3 object storage. Such an architecture (called streamhouse) makes it possible to process events in real time and at the same time store intermediate results in tabular form available for SQL queries. This solves the problem of batch/stream separation: instead of hours of waiting for batch updates, data becomes available for analytics almost instantly. Fig. 3 presents the architecture diagram of the implemented streaming pipeline.

Figure 3.

Architecture of the Yelp Streamhouse streaming platform (Apache Flink + Apache Paimon + Amazon S3) [7]

As a result of the transition to a streaming architecture, Yelp reduced the latency of analytical data from ~18 hours to a few minutes and reduced storage costs by 80% by moving data from Kafka brokers to inexpensive cloud storage. In addition, the simplification of the architecture (replacement of custom components with open tools) made it possible to significantly reduce operational overhead and increase platform reliability. Decentralization of storage (event data is written directly to S3 via Paimon) provided excellent fault tolerance – Amazon S3 object storage ensures data durability at the level of 99.99 %.

Another example is **Uber**, which moved data ingestion into its corporate Data Lake from batch mode to streaming in order to increase data freshness and reduce costs. Historically, data was aggregated with delays of hours or days, which slowed down experimentation and modeling. In 2025, Uber's engineering team developed a new system, IngestionNext, based on Apache Flink for continuous ingestion of events from Kafka into the data lake (in formats such as Apache Hudi). Architecturally, the solution is built using the Kafka message broker as a buffering layer and the Apache Flink streaming engine for continuous processing and writing of data to storage (fig. 4).

Figure 4. Architecture of the Uber streaming data ingestion pipeline [8]

The key motivation was to reduce data arrival time from hours to minutes, which directly accelerates the launch of new machine learning models and experiments, increasing the accuracy of analytics. Practical results confirmed the effectiveness of the solution: the streaming pipeline ensured data updates within minutes instead of hours and at the same time reduced the use of computing resources by approximately 25% compared to previous batch jobs. This means significant savings of cluster resources when processing petabyte-scale data volumes.

Alibaba uses Apache Flink in all key business processes – from personalization of recommendations and real-time dashboard updates during peak sales to instant fraud detection in fintech applications. Streaming analytics also optimizes logistics (real-time routing of deliveries), advertising (dynamic ad placement), and anomaly monitoring [9]. In addition, according to the official Google Cloud documentation, there are numerous examples of using Dataflow (an implementation of stream processing based on Apache Beam) for real-time ETL, scalable data integration, streaming analytics, and even integration with machine learning and artificial intelligence pipelines. Among the listed cases are the use of data for personalization, fraud analytics, and real-time marketing, as well as automatic scaling to thousands of worker nodes without manual configuration [10].

The practical experience of leading companies shows that the transition to a streaming architecture brings a scientifically grounded practical effect: data processing and decision-making are significantly accelerated, system stability and scalability are improved, and improvements in technical characteristics are converted into growth of business metrics and customer satisfaction. Streaming solutions have established themselves as a foundation for modern high-load services, allowing them to simultaneously achieve both high performance and development flexibility required for competitiveness in the digital economy.

3. Conclusion

Against the background of the steady growth of various data, the processing architecture becomes a key

factor determining the performance, scalability, and reliability of digital platforms. The streaming approach provides the possibility of processing events in real time, reduces the latency of obtaining analytical results, and increases the promptness of decision-making in business processes. The considered engineering principles of building streaming systems cover requirements for scaling, state management, fault tolerance, and load control. Architectural models based on event-driven interaction, component decomposition, and the use of distributed state storage make it possible to achieve stable operation under uneven and peak data streams.

Practical experience in implementing production solutions in various applied domains confirms the applicability of streaming architectures for high-load services. The use of specialized frameworks and cloud infrastructures contributes to reducing processing latency, increasing system stability, and more efficient use of computing resources. The combination of the considered approaches makes it possible to view stream processing as a basic architectural tool for designing modern big data systems, providing both technological flexibility and support for applied business tasks.

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